

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B361
Date: 02 May 2008
Take Off: 09:48:17
Landing: 12:52:18
Flight Time 3h 4m 1s

Campaign: Pre EUCAARI test flight

Operating Area: East Coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsey Rae	Directflight
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM
8	CPI rack	Ian Crawford	University of Manchester
9	AMS rack	James Allen	University of Manchester
10	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
11			
12			
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			

Flight Track:

B361 Track 02-MAY-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B361

Date: 02 May 08

Project: EUCAARI

Location: North East Coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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093342		Gin	0.17 kft	000	on; checked lat & lon
094817		T/O	0.16 kft	000	Cranfield
095007		cgps	3.0 kft	000	fixed/float cycling from t/o
095410		Nev	6.0 kft	000	liquid box zero biased hot
101129		Video	26.6 kft	000	#1 ffc , #2 ufc started
101246	102226	Run 1.1	27.0 kft	000	f1270
101302		bbr	27.0 kft	000	retract
101642		GIN	27.0 kft	000	long error - restart
101859		psap	27.0 kft	000	fault underreading 1.1 l/m (int)
101918		gin	27.0 kft	000	restart ok
102444	103436	Run 1.2	27.0 kft	000	
102521		nev	27.0 kft	000	zero
102638		JW	27.0 kft	000	zero
102726		Heimann	27.0 kft	000	cal 06
103237		satcom c	27.0 kft	000	recovered
103633	104308	Profile 1	27.0 - 20.0 kft	000	f1270 - f1200
104319	105309	Run 2.1	20.0 kft	000	f1200
104457		bbr retract	20.0 kft	000	
105609	110543	Run 2.2	20.0 kft	000	105506
110755	112630	Profile 2	20.1 - 5.0 kft	000	f1200 > f150
110835		bbr	19.7 kft	000	extend
111621		p2	13.0 kft	000	interrupt
111752		p2	13.0 kft	000	restart
112413		psap flow off	7.6 kft	000	cloud transit
112829	113838	Run 3.1	5.0 kft	000	
113603		bbr	5.0 kft	000	retract
114029	115029	Run 3.2	5.0 kft	000	
115230	115621	Profile 3	5.0 - 1.8 kft	000	
115640		qnh	1.8 kft	000	1019
115754	120753	Run 4.1	1.9 kft	000	
115917		bbr	1.9 kft	000	retract
120810	120951	Profile 4	1.9 - 0.86 kft	000	
120952	122021	Run 5.1	0.86 kft	000	
121335		heimann	0.86 kft	000	cal06
122039	122612	Profile 5	0.89 - 6.3 kft	000	
122347		psap flow	3.9 kft	000	off - cloud
122608		psap flow	6.1 kft	000	on
125218		Land	0.14 kft	000	cranfield

B361 Track 02-MAY-08

EUCAARI Test Flight B361
FAAM sortie brief

Friday 2 May, 2008

1. Pilot 1 (Directflight)
2. Pilot 2 (Directflight)
3. CCM (Directflight)
4. Core Chemistry - (FAAM)
5. Flight Manager - (FAAM)
6. CPI rack – Ian Crawford (Manchester)
7. AMS Rack – James Allan (Manchester)
8. CCN – Jamie Trembath
9. Mission Scientist -

Operating Area: C and D

Sortie Objectives: To test the 2DS and CAPS probes at high level and the ToF-AMS, CCN, and SMPS at low level

Weather. Low pressure system off Biscay and high pressure over north western continental Europe leading to slight W surface winds over the North Sea. Some Cu with associated showers are likely over the UK throughout the day but the forecast over the North Sea is for clear skies at 1200Z on 2 May. Aerosol forecasts suggests several aerosol plumes extending off the Essex and Suffolk coast and off the Yorkshire coast. The extent of the aerosol in these areas may depend on the extent of showers over land areas.

Define waypoints A and B on morning of flight. The points can be arbitrarily located but must be 10 minutes apart at science speed (require flight access between these points at levels: FL270; FL200; 5000', 2000'. Suggest the points are located off the Yorkshire coast.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off Cranfield at 10z (11 am local)
3. Transit to point A. [15 mins at transit]
4. Upon reaching point A conduct a SLR (at FL270) to point B. Turn on reciprocal heading and return to point A along SLR at FL270.. [20 min, T=35]
5. Turn, heading towards point, profile descent to arrive at point B at FL200. Turn on reciprocal heading and conduct two SLRs from B to A and then A to B. [30 min, T=65]

6. Conduct a broken profile descent to 5000' at 1000 ft/min to arrive at point B.
[15 min, T=80]
7. Turn towards point A and conduct two 10 minute SLRs on reciprocal headings between points A and B to arrive at B [20 min, T=105]
8. Profile descent to 2000' towards point A and then SLR to arrive at point A.
Turn towards point B and conduct two 10 minute SLRs on reciprocal headings between points A and B to arrive at A
[30 min, T=110]
9. Recover to Cranfield
[15 min, T=125]

Other comments:

Power on at 0700 local

Thursday 1 May 2008 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Friday 2 May 2008 12UTC
Surface: Mean sea level pressure / 12hr Accumulated precipitation (VT-6h/VT+6h)

Aerosol

At 15Z on 2/ 5/2008, from 03Z on 1/ 5/2008

Thursday 1 May 2008 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Friday 2 May 2008 12UTC
Low, L+M, Medium, M+H, High, H+L, H+M+L clouds

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B-56B** Date **02/05/08** Name **K.N. BOWER** Page **1** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					AMS servo not functioning -
10:36:06	KNB				Taxi start
10:48:25					Rolling
10:48:52					T/O
					CR 2300ft
					CR 2600ft Broken &
					CR 3000ft Broken
					CT 5950ft
					SMPS - ??
					CPC - shw heat - cond? - N
10:56:14					Climbing to FL270 - Clear air 360°
9.56.55 = 10:57:31	KNB				Serial server down - No Trach INU disco
10:00:30		15900			leak on CPC line - huge - OK
					CEN - gone above P ceiling - cabin air
					Tops Cu ahead 11 - 12,000ft - most ahead
10:06:13		FL230			Can see the pollution layer ahead
					Cloud pattern - mimick bird mess Flamborough
10:12:00	FL270	FL270			344mb 157m/s/360°
10:22:25	R1st				
					CIP - not cleared so struggling
					SPEE -17.4
					CAS Sensible
					CIP Occasional pr
					ZDS - functioning to a techon - elements
					stuck -

Fuel plw -28.14
 Laser 7. 20°
 -10
 Fuel V. vol - 18

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.361** Date **2/5/08** Name **K. N. BOWEN** Page **2** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	RUN 1.2	FL 270		NSS along coast	CPC / AMS / SMPS intake leaks on inlet
					OP2 - ZDS Meats threshold
10:33					T emp 7-8°C - 475 mbar on elements
10:34:32	R.12 end	FL 270			-45.22°C / -50.51°C 156 m/s / 360° 343 mb
10:36:25	P2 ↓				Going to FL 220
	P2 end				
					CPC - Alms sensor - center a bit low
10:43:06	R2.1	FL 200		S-N	(-30.32 / -39.6 464 mbar 134 m/s / 360° 130-120 odd 274.50 271.50
					High layer - ~ 20000 ft
					CEN ~ 100 CEN at 0.8 - inlet at both channels 15%
					AMS - along scan - shape of dist leak - CPC leak - not understood of DMA
					Smaller CPC reading on Core - some ~ leak
					CPI - CAS ✓ sensor
					CIP - inlet to scan
					ZDS threshold - maybe OK.
10:53:09	R2.1 end	FL 200			
10:55:06	R2.2 ↓	FL 200		S-N	-30.84 / -45.8° 139 / 360° 464 mb
11:05:37	R2.2 end				Scan OK -
					Still N ^o measurement above error by leak
11:07:52	P3 ↓	20000 → 5000			

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.36.1**... Date **2/5/08**... Name **R. N. BOWEN** Page **3** of **4**.

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11.16.06	P2 int	FL130		S-N	To turn to go S.
11.17.50	P2 con	FL130			
11.25.30					2DS X CIP ✓
					2DP - reg - no con
11.26.27	P2 end	FL050			-2.1°C -2.5°
					CPT - nothing
11.28.25	R3.1	FL050		S-N	-2.0°C / -1.74°C 113m/s 841mb
					FPSSP - saw shell
					CPT - cut trigger mode (so for nothing)
					SMPS scans - still nothing
11.33.59					dead
					CIP - seen shell ch1
					2DS - X
					CPT - X
11.38.30	R3.1 end	FL050		S-N	
11.40.26	R3.2 S	FL050		N-S	
					Scanning CPC - not seeing mol
					Jw - Nex TW - responding ✓
					↓ LWC fluctuating
11.50.24	R3.2 end	FL050		S-N	
11.52.28	P3 desc	FL050 - 2000			
		2400			2400 ft - CPC ↑ all particles con
11.50.20	P3 end	2000 ft			QOLN 1019.

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B...361...** Date **2/5/08** Name **K.N. BOWER** Page **4** of **4**.

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11.57.52	R4.1st	2000	N-S		SMPS Scanmo
					2DS - sensible T's - maybe still a problem
					More seen in BL
					At Alt - small leak.
					ADIENT EVASMI wad ✓
					CEN drp 2000 / 2400 0.3%
					CEN back up - so ^{SMPS} scans are good
					to be confirmed by Ais below
2.06.54					CEN - 6000 / cc - gang all set
					AMS v NO ₂ rich
12.07.50	R4.1end	2000			Descending
12.08.08	P4 sl	2000-1000			CEN - 50% Act ⁿ Spike at 0.3%
12.09.31	P4end	R.S.1st	1000/k.		
12.13.17	RS.1				20mm pellets - combustion - London + fish
12.20.19	RS.1end				
12.20.32	PS.				du
12.26.09	PSend				
1.52.54					landed

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 361

Date: 02/05/2008	Operator: pdr	DRS Time: 0	DAU1 Time: 0	DAU2 Time: 0	DAU3 Time: 0	Aux1 Time: 0	Aux2 Time: 0	Page 2 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:07:55	55	0.09														Start profile 2	
11:09:00	90	0.1															
11:10:00	120	0.11		5													
11:11:00	100	0.1		5													
11:12:00	140	0.12		10													
11:13:00	95	0.14		5													
11:14:00	120	0.11		5													
11:15:00	110	0.1		5													
11:16:21	40	0.11		0												Interrupt profile	
11:17:52	30	0.09		2												Recommence profile	
11:19:00	20	0.09		2													
11:20:00	30	0.1	263	0													
11:21:00	20			0													
11:22:00	45	0.09		0													
11:22:00	50	0.09		0													
11:23:00																	
11:24:00	30	0.1															
11:26:30	500	0.2	563	1000												End profile	
																Start run 3.1 FL 50	
11:30:00	350	0.09	580	10													
11:32:00	580	0.09	581	5													
11:34:00	850	0.09	1000	665												Going in and out of cloud	
11:36:00	600	0.09	768	10													
11:38:00	500	0.1	806	1000													
11:38:38	500	0.07	810	5												End run 3.1	
11:40:29	480	0.7	810	10												Start run 3.2 FL50	
11:42:30	700	0.08	974	10												Going in and out of cloud	
11:44:30	480	0.08	974	10												Spikes up to 2000 in clouds for SID1	
11:46:30	800	0.08	974	5													
11:48:30	500	0.1	974	5													
11:50:30	630	0.08	974	5												End run 3.2	
11:52:30	380	0.09	974	10												Start profile 3	
11:53:30	800	0.09		5													
11:54:30	750	0.11		5													
11:55:30	750	0.11		10													
11:56:20	690	0.1		10												End profile	
11:57:55	560	0.11		10													
12:00:00	1000	0.09		10													
12:02:00	500	0.09		10													
12:04:00	800	0.1		10													
12:06:00	940	0.08		10													
12:07:53	450	0.09		10												End run	
12:08:10																Start profile 4	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.8	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.6	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 0.6	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =7.9		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =0.8	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B361
Date of flight: 2/5/08

T/O:
Land:

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B361****Date of Flight:**

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	181810	Size of Bnnn.dat =
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read =41623 Blocks written = 41623 Bad reads =0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Start = 0 End = 240000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images A lot of noise in 2dp until near the end of the flight Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 0 End =240000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start =0 End = 240000</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat Y</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p> <p>checked</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size =1 Vol flow rate = 0.7
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check. checked

Flight:

B361

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:
 Heimann:
 Deiced Temp:
 Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:
 Buck CR2:
 General Eastern:
 Johnson Williams:
 Nevzorov:
 Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:
 Forward Facing:
 Rearward Facing:
 Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:
 GIN Applanix:
 INU Honeywell:
 Radar Altimeter:
 RVSM IAS:
 RVSM Static Pressure:
 XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:
 AVAPS:
 Cabin Pressure:
 Fax machine:
 Printer:
 S9 Static Pressure:
 Satcom C:
 Satcom H:
 Turb Centre-Static:
 Turb Left Right:
 Turb Up-Down:
 Turb Horizontal Chk:
 Turb Vertical Chk:
 Weather Radar:
DLUs:
 DLU AERACK:
 DLU BBR Lower:
 DLU BBR Upper:
 DLU Core Chem:
 DLU Core Consoles:
 DLU Port Aft:
 DLU Port Fwd:
 DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:
 BBR (clear) Lower:
 BBR (IR) Lower:
 BBR (red) Lower:
Upper:
 BBR (clear) Upper:
 BBR (IR) Upper:
 BBR (red) Upper:
 ARIES:
 DEIMOS:
 IR Camera:
 JNO2 Lower:
 JNO2 Upper:
 JO1D Lower:
 JO1D Upper:
 MARSS:
 SHIMS Lower:
 SHIMS Upper:
 SWS:
 TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:
 2DP:
 FFSSP:
 PCASP:
 2DS:
 ADA:
 CAPS:
 CCN:
 CDP:
 CIP 100:
 CIP 25:
 CPI:
 CVI:
 SID1:
 SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:
 CPC 3786 H2O:
 Filters 47mm:
 Filters 90mm:
 Neph - Dry:
 Neph - Wet:
 PSAP:
 AMS:
 CPC 3025 (AMS):
 INC:
 VACC:
 CPC 3010A (CVI):
 SP2:
 UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:
 NOx TE42C:
 Ozone TE49C:
 Ozone TE49:
 SO2 TE43C:
 TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 FAGE:
 Formaldehyde:
 NOx FAAM:
 NOxy:
 ORAC:
 PAN:
 PERCA:
 Peroxide:
 PTRMS:
 TDLAS (1C):
 WAS Bags:
 WAS Bottles:
Misc Non-Core
 CASI/ATM:
 LIDAR:
 LTI:
 SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B361

Date: 02 May 2008

Instruments

1. INU serial link failed during pre-flight – traced to decterm serial interface
Satcom c , neph serial link also down.
Bit more complex; looks as if processes that wait or poll eventually make intermittent contact, but those that are one shot are hit or miss
2. Nev liquid water zero biased 28 hot
3. TW status light on – heaters left in ‘off’ – recycled ok
4. Nev liquid water looks dead,
5. TW shows step at first cloud entry – not recovered

Flight B361 12:37:11
Heading 0 deg Speed 272 knots Height 5.9kft Press 812mb
Lat 0°0.0'N Long 0°0.0'E Wind 139 ms-1/360 deg
Temp -3.4C Dewpoint -2.78C
From 10:20:00 to now

Current values	
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	45429 secs
JAW LIQUID WATER CONTENT	0.1 g m-3
TOTAL WATER CONTENT	0.82 g kg
NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	0 g m-3
NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER	0.1 g m-3

All sc

several attempts to connect via ISDN
connection successful but terminated – no messages sent or rx

psap problem resolved – finger trouble

Status roundup

Aircraft

Nil

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B361:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Keith Bower
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
CPI log	CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
CCN	operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	24 Jul 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

1 x Forward Facing Cameras

1 x Upward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

?

?

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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